

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF SOCIALIZING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14957958>

Abstract. This thesis explores the pedagogical and psychological aspects of socializing primary school students. It discusses the achievements and challenges in this area.

Keywords: socialization, child psychology, teacher, social institutions, family, community, inclusive education.

As we know, due to the initiatives of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, there has been a significant increase in attention towards the younger generation [2]. Today's youth are advanced both intellectually and socially. Behind this, the state and the President have utilized all available resources to ensure that every child in the republic receives an education and plays a role in social life [3, 4].

It is important to note that today in the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are 9,691 general education schools (including 350 state specialized institutions where certain subjects are taught in-depth). The total number of students in general education schools is 5.8 million. Furthermore, 13,437 children with physical or mental developmental disabilities, who require long-term treatment, are being educated at home [4, 5].

The pedagogical and psychological aspects of socializing primary school students involve the processes of teaching students how to successfully adapt to society and build social relationships [6, 7]. These processes are especially important in primary education because, during this period, children develop key skills for self-awareness, communication with others, and adapting to society [8, 9].

The pedagogical and psychological aspects of socialization include the following:

1. Self-awareness (Identification): Primary school students begin to perceive themselves as part of society [10]. Social relationships between teachers and students play a significant role in this process [11].

2. Empathy and Understanding Others: Children learn to share their feelings with others and understand them [12]. Empathy, respect, and understanding for each other are the foundation of social interactions [13].

3. Developing Social Skills: Students learn social roles and acquire teamwork skills [14]. This, in turn, helps them to succeed in communication [15].

4. Working in Teams: Primary school students learn collaboration and teamwork [16]. Activities such as group assignments, games, and problem-solving together are crucial for developing these skills [17].

5. Collaboration between Teachers and Parents: Cooperation between teachers and parents is crucial in the socialization of students [18]. Parents should support their children during the learning process and help develop their social skills.

6. Emotional Stability: Children learn how to manage their emotions and resolve problems in a social environment. This ensures their psychological stability [19,20].

7. Familiarization with Laws and Rules: Students learn about the social rules, laws, and norms in society. This helps them understand their place in the social system [21, 22].

The teacher's role in the socialization of primary school students is significant because they guide students in learning social skills, providing psychological support, and building mutual respect. This process lays the foundation for social adaptation and ensures that students adjust to society [23].

It is also important to mention that the socialization of children with physical or psychological developmental disorders is of great importance. In this case, parents must adopt a more responsible approach towards their child. If parents view such children as full members of society, secondary socialization challenges can be minimized [24]. Unfortunately, there are obstacles to convincing these children that they are part of society, like a lack of attention and communication with them or a lack of interest in their abilities. This requires pedagogues to address each student based on their needs and abilities [25].

The "Concept for the Development of the Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" also highlights these issues. The concept emphasizes that teachers must primarily be motivators. It also emphasizes that providing special attention to children, especially those with disabilities or orphans, and helping them open opportunities is a major goal and responsibility [1, 2].

From the above, it is clear that the development of a child's personality and establishing their place in society is the responsibility not only of the teacher but also of the school's leadership and parents. The socialization process of students is an issue that needs attention not only at school but also in the family [26].

Behind every person who achieves high social milestones is a dedicated teacher and an engaged parent, and unfortunately, in the opposite scenario, every unsocialized individual has their first teacher and parents to thank. Keeping this in mind, we, as primary school teachers, must devote specific moments in every lesson to socializing the child. The smallest form of socialization is teaching children the etiquette of greeting [27].

However, there are students who only greet teachers they know or fear, which is common among younger primary students [28]. This indicates that such a child will only be successful working with a familiar group in the future. If we fail to successfully guide children through such small but important steps, socialization gaps will inevitably appear. Therefore, in every lesson, we must set aside 3-4 minutes as a socialization moment. Another important aspect of socialization is the activities outside the classroom and school [29]. By taking children on various excursions, we introduce them to new environments, helping them adapt to unfamiliar things and people [30].

We can organize trips to museums, gardens, or parks, which will serve both educational and social purposes. These places are usually crowded with people, allowing children to learn how to adapt to new social situations and interact with strangers.

In conclusion, we can say that every person needs socialization. The primary responsibility for socializing primary school students lies in the hands of their teachers, and this should never be forgotten. Pedagogical and psychological approaches to socializing primary school students are of great importance. Every student has a unique psychology, requiring a personalized approach. This calls for creativity and high skill from pedagogues. A skilled teacher will use all available resources to ensure that every student grows into a mature individual in the future.

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